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EFFECT OF FIRM ATTRIBUTES ON STOCK RETURNS OF QUOTED COMPANIES IN NIGERIA

¹AKINBORODE Akeem, ²ABDULLAHI Musa Abdullahi, ¹IYERE Samuel Iheonkhan

¹Department of Accounting, Faculty of Administration, Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria

²Department of Taxation, Faculty of Administration, Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

AKINBORODE AKEEM

National Commission for Colleges of Education

Abuja Nigeria

akeemlovesyou@gmail.com

+2347084980000; +2348037878666

ABSTRACT

Stock returns are a fundamental concept in finance, representing the gain or loss realized by an investor from holding a stock over a specific period. This study examined the effect of firm attributes; profitability, liquidity, firm size, leverage and dividend policy, on stock returns of quoted companies in Nigeria for 2015-2024. Population of the study comprised of firm listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGXGroup). 27 firms were sampled based on market capitalization as at 31st December, 2024. Employing an ex-post facto research design and a purposive sampling method, the study utilized secondary data sourced from the NGXGroup and the annual reports of the sampled firms. Stock returns was measured by the all-share index (ASI) of the NGXGroup, profitability was proxied by return on equity (ROE), liquidity was proxied by current ratio (CRR), firm size was proxied by market capitalization (Mcap), leverage was proxied debt-equity ratio (DER) and dividend policy was proxied by dividend payout ratio (DPR). Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics as well as panel regression models. Findings revealed that profitability (ROE) and leverage (DER) both exhibited negative but statistically insignificant relationships with ASI. Liquidity (CRR) showed a positive yet insignificant effect, firm size (Mcap) demonstrated a strong and statistically significant negative effect on ASI, while dividend policy (DPR) emerged as the only variable with a positive and statistically significant impact on stock returns. The study recommended amongst others, that quoted companies should prioritize consistent and transparent dividend policies and that investors, companies and analysts should be cautious in relying solely on ROE as a measure of performance.

KEYWORDS: Stock Returns, Market Capitalization, Emerging Economies, Quoted Companies, Market Volatility.

INTRODUCTION

In the dynamic landscape of financial markets, stock returns remain a central concern for investors, corporate managers, and policymakers alike. In emerging economies such as Nigeria, the stock market plays a pivotal role in capital formation, resource allocation, and economic development (Salisu & Lawan, 2018). Capital markets, where stocks are traded serve as key vehicles for investment and wealth creation, making the determinants of stock returns a subject of enduring relevance. Stock returns are a fundamental concept in finance, representing the gain or loss realized by an investor from holding a stock over a specific period. This return is typically expressed as a percentage of the initial investment and is composed of two key components: capital gains, which arise from changes in the stock's market price, and income returns, usually in the form of dividends. Brealey et al. (2020) defined stock return as the total income from an investment, emphasizing that both price appreciation and dividend income must be considered to accurately assess performance. Modigliani and Pogue (1973) described return as the "reward for investing," highlighting its central role in evaluating financial decisions. Campbell and Viceira (2002) further elaborated that stock returns are stochastic outcomes influenced by firm-specific fundamentals, macroeconomic conditions and investor expectations, making them essential to asset pricing and portfolio management. Scholars measure stock returns using various approaches that reflect both historical performance and investor gains. Such measures include total return or dividend-adjusted return, Market Returns (Index-Based) and Stock Price Changes. This study adopted Index-Based with the use of Nigerian Exchange Group All Share Index (ASI), not only because its use is consistent with contemporary studies, but also that ASI captures the performance of all listed equities on the exchange, offering a comprehensive view of the

market rather than focusing on individual stocks or sectors. It serves as a benchmark for fund managers, analysts, and researchers. Thus, using it as the proxy for the dependent variable allowed for easier comparison across studies and aligned with industry standards.

Firm attributes are the internal characteristics and structural features of a company that influence its financial performance, strategic behaviour, and market valuation. These attributes are typically categorized into financial attributes, such as profitability, liquidity, leverage, firm size, and growth potential and non-financial attributes, including firm age, management competence, ownership structure, board composition, and operational scope. Rabi (2021), opined that firm attributes are unique characteristics that shape stakeholder perceptions and influence firm performance and future prospects while Shehu (2012) defined firm attributes as internal variables that influence corporate policy and decision-making. Similarly, Oluwatayo et al. (2019) posited that firm attributes are identified internal structures, unique strategies and distinctive profiles of organisations, which are resource-based, that affect the performance and success of the business while Abdullahi (2016) submitted that firm attributes refer to the various information reported by firms in their financial statements for a particular accounting period which can send a message to various stakeholders of firms about their performance.

Several empirical studies have examined the factors influencing stock performance and returns. Fama and French (1992) highlighted the "size effect" and "value effect," showing that smaller firms and those with high book-to-market ratios tend to outperform others. Profitability has also been positively linked to stock returns, as financially strong firms attract investors due to their growth prospects (Haugen & Baker, 1996). Leverage presents a more complex relationship;

while it can boost returns during economic expansions, it also increases risk during downturns, as shown by Bhandari (1988). Liquidity enhances stock appeal by lowering transaction costs, thereby improving returns (Amihud & Mendelson, 1986). Modigliani and Miller (1961) proposed the Dividend Irrelevance Theory, suggesting that under perfect market conditions, dividend decisions do not affect firm value. In contrast, Black and Scholes (1973) explored how dividend policy can influence stock prices and returns, contributing to the broader debate on its relevance.

While these global insights provided a useful framework, the Nigerian context presents unique conditions that necessitate localized investigation. Interestingly, firm attributes have long been recognized as critical factors influencing stock performance. These attributes, which include profitability, liquidity, firm size, leverage, and dividend policy, encapsulate the internal dynamics of a company and its strategic decisions. They shape investor perceptions, affect risk profiles, and ultimately determine the attractiveness of a firm's stock. Profitability stands out as a fundamental indicator of financial health. Profitable firms are generally more attractive to investors, as they signal operational efficiency and the potential for sustainable growth (Hada & Mihalcea, 2020). Liquidity, which reflects a firm's ability to meet short-term obligations, influences investor confidence, particularly in uncertain economic environments (Naidoo et al., 2025). Firm size, often measured by market capitalization or total assets, can affect stock returns through economies of scale, market power, and stability (Astakhov et al., 2019). Leverage, or the extent of debt financing, introduces both opportunities and risks while it can amplify returns, it also increases financial vulnerability (Murombi & Mohammed, 2024). Dividend policy serves as a signal of corporate governance and financial discipline, with consistent dividend payments often viewed as a

sign of stability and investor-friendly management (Narang et al., 2023). While other variables such as macroeconomic factors also play a role as determinants of stock returns, firm-level characteristics offer a more granular and actionable lens through which stock returns can be understood and forecasted (Kogan & Papanikolaou, 2012; Egbunike & Okerekeoti, 2018).

Despite the theoretical and empirical significance of these attributes, existing literature have produced divergent, mixed and sometimes contradictory findings regarding their impact on stock returns. For instance, while Anggraini and Wijayanto (2021) found profitability significantly influences returns, Augustine et al. (2024) reported an insignificant effect. Liquidity was deemed irrelevant by Cakici and Zaremba (2021) outside microcap stocks, yet Adegbite and Oladipo (2022) found a positive impact. Firm size showed contrasting results between Wairimu (2017) and Yuliarti and Diyani (2018). Leverage was linked positively by Aharon et al. (2019), negatively by Andersson (2016) and Adami et al. (2010), and insignificantly by Sefti (2021). These inconsistencies underscore the need for context-specific research that accounts for the unique characteristics of the Nigerian market.

Again, a review of prior studies revealed another gap in the literature. While existing literature has explored the effect of firm attributes on stock returns, most studies have focused on developed markets, with limited research conducted in emerging economies like Nigeria. Also, many studies focused predominantly on macroeconomic variables or have examined firm attributes in isolation. Few studies have adopted a comprehensive approach that jointly considers multiple firm-level factors using robust metrics and methodologies. This study, whose main objective is to evaluate the effect of firm attributes on stock returns of quoted firms in Nigeria, aims to fill these identified gaps by

addressing all these dimensions. Specifically, the study also intends to determine the respective effect of profitability, liquidity, firm size, leverage and dividend policy on stock returns of quoted firms in Nigeria. The findings are expected to offer practical implications for investors seeking to optimize their portfolios, corporate managers aiming to enhance firm value, and policymakers striving to improve market efficiency and transparency.

The study was structured into five parts. Part one was the introduction. Part two comprised of conceptual framework, empirical review and the theoretical framework. Part three was the methodology, part four contained the discussion of findings and the final part was the conclusion and recommendations.

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

▪ Stock Returns

Stock returns represent the financial gain or loss realized by investors from holding equity securities over a period. Stock returns are broadly defined as the percentage change in the value of a stock, typically accounting for both capital gains and income components such as dividends (Frankel, 2025; Investopedia, 2025). Stock return is precious to investors as it is the primary purpose of investment in ordinary shares. It thus serves as critical performance indicators for investors, firms, and policymakers alike. Brealey et al. (2020) posited that total return is the most comprehensive measure, capturing both price movements and dividend payouts, and is essential for evaluating investment performance. From a theoretical standpoint, stock returns are central to asset pricing models. The Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM), introduced by Sharpe (1964), posited that expected stock returns are a function of systematic risk, measured by beta, and the market risk premium. The CAPM thus laid the foundation for more nuanced models like the Fama-French Three-Factor and Five-Factor

Models, which incorporated additional factors to explain variations in returns (Fama & French, 1992 and 2015).

▪ Firm Attributes

Firm attributes, often referred to as firm characteristics, refer to the characteristics and internal factors that influence a company's performance, financial structure, and overall market valuation. Firm attributes refer to unique characteristics and qualities that play significant roles in determining the price and returns of equity in the stock markets. These attributes include profitability, liquidity, firm size, leverage, dividend policy, operational efficiency, corporate governance, and sustainability practices.

➤ Profitability

Profitability reflects a firm's ability to generate earnings from its operations and investments over a specific period. Hada and Mihalcea (2020) regarded profitability as a core indicator of economic efficiency and financial health. The duo submitted that profitability is essential for assessing the performance of economic entities, as it summarizes the outcome of managerial decisions and operational effectiveness through metrics like return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE), and return on sales (ROS). Nissim (2023) expanded this view by decomposing profitability into components such as profit margin and asset turnover, emphasizing its role in forecasting, valuation, and earnings quality analysis.

➤ Liquidity

Liquidity refers to a firm's ability to meet its short-term obligations using readily available assets. Mishkin (2006) viewed liquidity as a critical indicator of financial flexibility and operational resilience and thus ensures that firms can respond to unexpected cash flow needs without incurring significant losses, thereby

maintaining investor confidence and market stability. Lippman and McCall (1986) offered an operational perspective, defining liquidity as the ease with which assets can be converted into cash without affecting their market price. More broadly, Ortiz (2020) emphasized that liquidity is not only a technical measure but also a reflection of trust and information symmetry among market participants, making it central to financial market functioning and regulation.

➤ **Firm Size**

Firm size refers to the scale or magnitude of a company. It is a measure of how big or small a company is and a crucial determinant in assessing a firm's competitiveness, market influence, and operational capabilities. Empirical studies often measure firm size using proxies such as total assets, market capitalization, sales revenue, or number of employees, each capturing different dimensions of scale and influence. Hashmi et al. (2020) submitted that firm size significantly affects key financial practices, including investment policy, dividend decisions, and governance structures, highlighting its strategic role in shaping corporate outcomes. Dang et al. (2018) further emphasized that, the choice of firm size proxy can materially influence empirical results, a phenomenon known as the "measurement effect," which underscores the need for theoretical and contextual justification when selecting size indicators. These scholarly views affirmed that firm size is not merely a descriptive metric but a dynamic variable with broad implications for financial analysis and decision-making.

➤ **Leverage**

Leverage refers to the strategic use of borrowed capital to increase the potential return on investment. Scholars widely recognize it as a double-edged tool capable of amplifying gains but also heightening financial risk. According to Hayes (2025), leverage allows firms to undertake

growth initiatives without diluting ownership, but it also exposes them to greater vulnerability during economic downturns. Laila and Akhter (2021) averred that financial leverage affects key performance indicators such as return on equity and earnings per share, noting that while higher leverage can enhance profitability, it may also strain a firm's financial position if not managed prudently. Firestone (2012) added that understanding leverage requires a nuanced grasp of both its empowering potential and its inherent risks, especially in volatile markets. These views underscored leverage as a critical component of capital structure decisions, balancing opportunity with caution.

➤ **Dividend Policy**

Dividend policy refers to the strategic decisions firms make regarding the distribution of profits to shareholders, typically in the form of cash dividends. Scholars viewed it as a core component of corporate financial management, with implications for firm value, investor perception, and capital structure. According to Said (2024), dividend policy is one of the most debated topics in finance, as it can significantly influence firm performance depending on how and when dividends are paid. Mafiejor (2021) emphasized that dividend decisions reflect managerial confidence and signal financial health, often attracting different types of investors based on payout patterns. Classic theories such as the Dividend Irrelevance Theory by Modigliani and Miller (1961) argued that under perfect market conditions, dividend policy does not affect firm value, while signaling theory and the bird-in-hand hypothesis suggest that consistent dividends can reduce uncertainty and enhance investor trust. These perspectives highlight dividend policy as both a financial tool and a communication mechanism within capital markets.

▪ Empirical Review

Empirical studies have been conducted to assess the influence of firm attributes on stock returns of companies in diverse sectors of the economy both domestically and internationally. Adebite and Olayemi (2022), Stephen and Davianti (2021), Lusiana (2020), Jeroh (2020), and Owolabi and Obida (2018) found a significant positive relationship between profitability and stock returns. This implies that profitable firms tend to attract investor interest, likely due to their operational efficiency and potential for sustainable growth. Contrarily, Sulastri et al. (2024), Agustine et al. (2024), Ezeani (2019) and Yulianti and Diyani (2018) reported either negative or statistically insignificant relationships between profitability and stock returns, contradicting signalling theory which posited that financial indicators should influence investor behaviour. The findings of the latter studies indicated that profitability may not always translate into improved market performance.

Examining the relationship between liquidity and stock returns, Boateng and Osei (2024), Chen and Wang (2023), Kim and Park (2023), Chen and Lee (2022), Sharma and Singh (2020) and Boloupremo (2020) found a significant positive relationship between liquidity and stock returns. This suggests that firms with stronger liquidity positions are better equipped to meet short-term obligations, which enhances investor confidence and market valuation. However, Adebayo and Okonkwo (2021) found a significant negative effect of liquidity on stock returns indicating that liquidity may not be a decisive factor in all contexts. The conclusions of Cakici and Zaremba (2021) and Ezeani (2019) revealed that liquidity had no significant relationship with stock returns.

In conducting an assessment of the effect of firm size on companies' stock returns, Lailliyah et al. (2024), Putri and Kufepaksi (2023), Etale et al. (2020), and Agbam and Anyamaobi (2018) reported a significant positive relationship

between firm size and stock returns. This implies that larger firms benefit from economies of scale, operational stability, and investor trust. Contrarily, the findings by Sosa et al. (2024), Ali et al. (2023), Babarinde (2022) and Farhan and Sharif (2021) revealed a significant negative correlation between firm size and stock returns, indicating that smaller firms tend to offer higher returns compared to larger firms. The findings of the latter studies indicated that as the size of the firm increase, the stock returns decrease. In other words, there is higher returns on investment on smaller firms than larger firms, a scenario that explained why investors demand a higher premium for investing in smaller firms due to the higher risk associated with them. Yulianti and Diyani (2018), Ezeani (2019), and Ojo and Salami (2022) found insignificant relationship between firm size and stock returns, suggesting that size alone may not drive returns in all contexts.

Studies conducted by Obi and Nworie (2024), Chauhan (2023), Ogudo et al. (2023) and Afolabi and Olaniyan (2021) on the effect of leverage on stock returns found a significant positive correlation between the explanatory variable and the endogenous variable, implying that financial institutions can use debt strategically to expand operations and improve returns. However, Rutfors and Olausson (2025), Yermiana et al. (2022), Ali and Khan (2020), Andersson (2016), and Adami et al. (2010) reported negative relationships, indicating that higher leverage levels are associated with lower stock performance and that high leverage may expose firms to both systemic and financial risks, reduced investors' confidence and increased regulatory scrutiny. Studies by Oktasari et al. (2025), Nguavese (2021) and Sefti (2021) found the relationship between leverage and stock return insignificant.

Isibor and Ehiedu (2025), Amah et al. (2025), Lawal and Kareem (2024), Caesaro et al. (2023)

and Afolabi and Olaniyan (2021) examined the effect of dividend payout on stock returns of companies operating in the different sectors of the economy and indicated that dividend payouts positively and significantly influenced stock returns, indicating that stable payouts enhance investor trust and confidence. However, Putra et al. (2024), Maulana et al. (2023), Agbo and Nwankwo (2023), Thuvvara et al. (2018) and Okoye and Eze (2017) found insignificant relationship between dividend payouts and stock returns suggesting that while regular dividend payments might appeal to investors, they do not necessarily translate into higher returns in all context. The conclusions of the latter studies challenged the traditional signaling theory, which posited that stable and generous dividend payouts signalled firm strength and should positively influence investor sentiment and share performance.

Based on the above conceptual review, the following hypotheses were formulated.

H_{0.1}: Profitability has no significant effect on stock returns of quoted companies in Nigeria.

H_{0.2}: Liquidity has no significant effect on stock returns of quoted companies in Nigeria.

H_{0.3}: Firm size has no significant effect on stock returns of quoted companies in Nigeria.

H_{0.4}: Leverage has no significant effect on stock returns of quoted companies in Nigeria.

H_{0.5}: Dividend policy has no significant effect on stock returns of quoted companies in Nigeria.

▪ **Resource-Based Theory**

This study was anchored on Resource-Based Theory (RBT), primarily articulated by Jay Barney in his 1991 seminal paper. RBT asserted that a firm's lasting competitive edge stemmed from its ability to acquire and utilize valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable (VRIN) resources. These assets, either tangible or

intangible, must be effectively organized and leveraged to help firms outperform rivals and achieve superior returns. RBT shifted focus from external market positioning to internal capabilities, arguing that firms differ in their resource endowments and that these differences explain variations in performance. However, critics of RBT have pointed out its limitations, which include its vague definitions of what constitutes a "resource," its lack of empirical measurability, and its tendency to overlook dynamic market conditions and external threats. Despite these critiques, RBT remains influential, especially in studies examining firm-level determinants of success. Firm attributes such as profitability, liquidity, firm size, leverage, and dividend policy are considered as internal resources that influence investor perception and, consequently, stock performance. The theory thus provided a strong framework to assess how firm-specific traits, when well-managed, can become strategic assets that boost market performance.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted ex-post facto research design. It is a quasi-experimental method which explores how an independent variable influence a dependent variable. The data used in the study combined both cross-sectional (firms) and time-series (multiple years) dimensions. Panel regression effectively combines these two dimensions, allowing for a more comprehensive analysis of the relationship between firm attributes and the endogenous variable, stock returns. This made the design aligned with the causal and quantitative nature of the research, making it a strong methodological choice.

The population of the study comprised all the quoted companies on the Nigeria Exchange Group (NGX) on or before 2014. These companies were ranked from top to bottom based on their market capitalization as at 31st December 2024. Twenty-seven (27) top companies were

selected using purposive sampling technique based on the set criteria. The criteria were to ensure availability of consistent data for the ten-year period (2015–2024) required for robust data analysis. Data deployed in this study were exclusively secondary in nature. The secondary data were sourced from the NGXGroup and the annual reports and accounts of the selected companies over the ten-year period. The timeframe was meticulously chosen to ensure that the study captures a sufficiently long horizon to analyze trends and relationships while accounting

Model Specification

$$SR_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 PRF_{it} + \beta_2 LIQ_{it} + \beta_3 FMS_{it} + \beta_4 LEV_{it} + \beta_5 DVP_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

where:

SR represents Stock Returns measured by NSE All-Share Index (ASI);

PRF represents Profitability measured by Return on Earnings (ROE);

LIQ represents Liquidity measured by the Current Ratio (CRR);

FMS represents Firm Size measured by the Market Capitalization (Mcap);

LEV represents Leverage measured by the Debt-Equity Ratio (DER);

DVP represents Dividend Policy measured by the Dividend Pay-out Ratio (DPR);

α represents the constant;

β_1, β_5 represent the coefficients of the explanatory variables;

μ represents the error term;

i represents the cross-sectional dimension;

t represents the time series effect.

for significant regulatory and governance changes during this period. The selected companies cut across different sectors of the Nigerian economy.

To establish the effect of firms' attributes on stock returns of quoted companies in Nigeria, which was the primary objective of this study, panel regression technique was deployed. This technique is particularly suitable for analyzing datasets that combine cross-sectional and time-series dimensions, making it ideal for this study.

Table 1: Operationalization of Variables

Variables	Proxy	Description	Reference
Stock Returns	NSE All Share Index (ASI)	All Share Index as at 31 st December every year	Akwe (2018), Ntshangase et al. (2016), Khalid & Khan (2017).
Profitability	Return On Equity (ROE)	$\frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Shareholders Equity}}$	Zhofiroh & Arifin (2023), Nugraha et al. (2023), Nadyayani & Suarjaya (2021).
Liquidity	Current Ratio	$\frac{\text{Current Assets}}{\text{Current Liabilities}}$	Olagunju et al. (2021), Garba (2020), Listyaningsih (2020).
Firm Size	Market Capitalization	Natural logarithm of number of outstanding shares of the firm at year end multiplied by share price of the same financial year	Chukwuma et al. (2023), Peter et al. (2020), Dang (2018),
Leverage	Debt-to-Equity Ratio (DER)	$\frac{\text{Total Liabilities}}{\text{Shareholders Equity}}$	Ogudo et al. (2023), Aharon & Yagil (2019).
Dividend Policy	Dividend Pay-out Ratio (DPR)	$\frac{\text{Dividend per Share}}{\text{Earnings per Share}}$	Olufemi & Blessing (2024), Caesaro et al. (2023), Osakwe et al. (2019).

Source: Author's compilation 2025

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
SR	270	46397.11	23377.19	26842.07	102926.4
PRF	270	.1141436	1.581548	-25.33779	1.872808
LIQ	270	1.084222	.8067641	.0810993	9.028202
FMS	270	25.77238	1.45947	22.25509	29.7203
LEV	270	5.10523	7.288908	-10.30436	103.6188
DVP	270	.4377248	.548472	-2.38806	4.545455

Source: Stata 17 Data analysis output

Stock Returns (SR) had a mean of 46,397.11 and a standard deviation of 23,377.19, indicating high variability across sampled firms. Profitability (PRF) averaged 0.1141 with a standard deviation of 1.58; the highly negative minimum value showed some firms suffered major losses,

eroding equity. The wide spread reflected uneven profitability. Liquidity (LIQ) averaged 1.08 with a 0.81 standard deviation, suggesting firms generally had just enough current assets to meet liabilities, indicating moderate liquidity. Firm Size (FMS) had a mean of 25.77 and a standard deviation of 1.46, showing more stability than profitability and liquidity. The high average implied most firms were large-cap, typical of listed Nigerian companies. Leverage (LEV) averaged 5.10 with a high standard deviation of 7.29; negative values indicated firms with negative equity, while values above 100 show extreme reliance on debt. Dividend Policy (DVP) had a mean of 0.4377 and a standard deviation of 0.55, suggesting Nigerian firms distributed about 44% of earnings to shareholders.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix Table

	SR	PRF	LIQ	FMS	LEV	D
SR	1.0000					
PRF	0.0316	1.0000				
LIQ	0.0614	0.0609	1.0000			
FMS	-0.2094	0.0455	-0.2484	1.0000		
LEV	-0.0872	-0.8130	-0.0800	-0.0498	1.0000	
DVP	0.1492	0.0812	0.1067	0.1091	-0.1237	1.00

Source: Stata 17 Data analysis output

The correlation analysis revealed linear relationships between stock returns (SR) and explanatory variables. Profitability showed a very weak positive correlation with SR ($r = 0.0316$), indicating only marginal association. Liquidity also had a weak positive link ($r = 0.0614$), suggesting it doesn't significantly drive SR, as investors may prioritize growth and dividends over short-term solvency. Firm size was negatively correlated with SR ($r = -0.2094$), aligning with regression results and agency theory (Jensen & Meckling, 1976), which suggests larger firms face inefficiencies that reduce returns. Leverage showed a weak negative correlation with SR ($r = -0.0872$), consistent with regression findings. A strong negative correlation between leverage and profitability ($r = -0.8130$) implied high debt lowered profitability and thus SR. Dividend policy had a moderate positive correlation with SR ($r = 0.1492$), supporting signaling theory (Bhattacharya, 1979), which viewed dividends as signals of firm strength that boost investor confidence and returns.

Table 4: Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity

Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity
 Ho: Constant variance
 Variables: fitted values of SR

chi2(1) = 0.85
 Prob > chi2 = 0.356

Source: Stata 17 Data analysis output

The Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test affirmed that the residuals of the regression model exhibited constant variance, supporting the assumption of homoskedasticity. The study therefore failed to reject the null hypothesis. The result strengthened the reliability of the regression analysis and ensures that the conclusions drawn from the model are valid.

Table 5: Multicollinearity test

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
LEV	2.99	0.334935
PRF	2.95	0.338659
LIQ	1.09	0.914251
FMS	1.09	0.916618
DVP	1.05	0.956714
Mean VIF	1.83	

Source: Stata 17 Data analysis output

The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values were all below 10, with a mean VIF of 1.83, indicating the absence of multicollinearity among the explanatory variables (Gujarati & Porter, 2009). This assures the reliability of the estimated coefficients.

Table 6: Hausman Test

```

----- Coefficients -----
      |      (b)      (B)      (b-B)      sqrt(diag(V_b-V_B))
      |      fe      re      Difference      S.E.
-----+-----
PRF | -3254.079 -1527.491 -1726.589 2300.948
LIQ | 1314.95 -633.4446 1948.394 1170.036
FMS | -13378.63 -3786.328 -9592.306 1729.425
LEV | -977.304 -526.942 -450.362 563.5828
DVP | 8071.469 7047.635 1023.834 1234.892
-----+-----
      b = consistent under Ho and Ha; obtained from xtreg
      B = inconsistent under Ha, efficient under Ho; obtained from xtreg

Test: Ho: difference in coefficients not systematic

      chi2(5) = (b-B)'[(V_b-V_B)^(-1)](b-B)
              = 44.12
      Prob>chi2 = 0.0000
      (V_b-V_B is not positive definite)
    
```

Source: Stata 17 Data analysis output

The Hausman test was conducted to determine whether the fixed effects (FE) or random effects (RE) model is more appropriate for this analysis. The null hypothesis (H_0) assumes that the differences in coefficients between the two models are not systematic, implying that the random effects model is suitable. The test statistic yielded a $\chi^2 = 0.0000$ which is less than the conventional significance level of 0.05. The result affirmed rejection of the null hypothesis, indicating that systematic differences exist and therefore Fixed Effects model is appropriate for the panel regression.

Table 7: Fixed Effects Model

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Fixed-effects (within) regression      Number of obs = 270
Group variable: ID                    Number of groups = 27

R-sq: within = 0.2256                  Obs per group: min = 10
      between = .                        avg = 10.0
      overall = 0.0675                   max = 10

corr(u_i, Xb) = -0.8371                 F(5,238) = 13.87
                                          Prob > F = 0.0000
-----+-----
      SR |      Coef.      Std. Err.      t      P>|t|      [95% Conf. Interval]
-----+-----
PRF | -3254.079 2744.644 -1.19 0.237 -8660.978 2152.819
LIQ | 1314.95 2134.448 0.62 0.538 -2889.874 5519.774
FMS | -13378.63 1990.527 -6.72 0.000 -17299.93 -9457.333
LEV | -977.304 651.304 -1.50 0.135 -2260.361 305.7528
DVP | 8071.469 2848.539 2.83 0.005 2459.899 13683.04
_cons | 391598.3 50545.29 7.75 0.000 292025 491171.6
-----+-----
sigma_u | 17282.13
sigma_e | 21870.919
rho | .38438676 (fraction of variance due to u_i)
-----+-----
F test that all u_i=0: F(26, 238) = 1.67 Prob > F = 0.0248
    
```

Source: Stata 17 Data analysis output

The dataset included 270 observations from 27 listed Nigerian companies over a decade. The model accounted for 22.56% of stock return variation, as shown by the R-squared value. Rho indicated that 38.4% of this variation stemmed from firm-specific differences. The F test ($p = 0.0240$) confirmed these effects were statistically significant, validating the use of the Fixed Effects model. A strong negative correlation (-0.8371) between firm effects and predictors further supported this choice.

Regression results showed profitability, measured by return on equity (ROE), had a negative but insignificant link with ASI. This

implied higher profitability doesn't necessarily lead to better stock returns. Accounting-based ratios might not reflect investor-perceived value, especially in less efficient markets like Nigeria. Otegunrin et al. (2021) also noted ROE's weak link to shareholder returns when confidence in earnings is low.

Liquidity, represented by the current ratio (CRR), showed a positive but insignificant relationship with ASI. While firms with better liquidity can meet short-term obligations, this doesn't guarantee higher shareholder returns. Investors might see high liquidity as underutilized capital rather than growth potential. Enekwe, Agu, and Eziedo (2014) similarly found liquidity ratios had limited impact on stock returns in Nigerian firms.

Firm size, measured by market capitalization (Mcap), had a strong, significant negative effect on ASI. Contrary to expectations, larger firms don't yield higher returns. The finding supported the view that big firms face inefficiencies and agency costs, as per Jensen and Meckling (1976). Abiodun (2019) also found a negative link between Mcap and shareholder value in Nigeria, suggesting size doesn't ensure better returns in emerging markets.

Leverage, measured by the debt-equity ratio (DER), showed a negative but insignificant relationship with ASI. Although theory have suggested that high debt raises financial risk and lowers returns, the insignificance result implied investors might not prioritize capital structure in Nigerian markets. This aligned with pecking order theory (Myers & Majluf, 1984), which suggested firms prefer internal financing, and that debt might not signal much in underdeveloped credit environments.

Dividend policy, indicated by the dividend pay-out ratio (DPR), had a positive and significant impact on ASI. The result highlighted dividends'

role in boosting shareholder value, supporting signaling theory (Bhattacharya, 1979). The positive link suggested investors see dividends as signs of firm strength and growth. Uwuigbe et al. (2012) also reported that in Nigeria's less efficient markets, dividends strongly influence stock returns as proof of performance.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study investigated the effect of firm attributes on stock returns of quoted companies in Nigeria. The findings revealed a complex and context-sensitive relationship between firm characteristics and stock performance.

Profitability (ROE) and leverage (DER) both exhibited negative but statistically insignificant relationships with ASI, suggesting that traditional financial indicators might not reliably predict stock returns in the Nigerian market. Liquidity (CRR) showed a positive yet insignificant effect, indicating that while firms might be financially stable, excess liquidity does not necessarily translate into investor value.

Firm size (Mcap) demonstrated a strong and statistically significant negative effect on ASI, challenging conventional wisdom and highlighting the potential inefficiencies associated with large corporate structures in emerging markets. In contrast, dividend policy (DPR) emerged as the only variable with a positive and statistically significant impact on stock returns (ASI), reinforcing the importance of dividend signals in investor decision-making within less efficient capital markets.

With regards to these discoveries, the three null hypotheses H_{0-1} , H_{0-2} and H_{0-4} , were therefore accepted while H_{0-3} and H_{0-5} were rejected. Overall, the results suggested that Nigerian investors may place greater emphasis on tangible and transparent indicators such as dividend pay-outs, while remaining skeptical of accounting-

based metrics and capital structure signals. This underscored the need for firms to align financial strategies with investor expectations and market realities.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were suggested for investors, policymakers, regulators, and stakeholders in the diverse sectors of the Nigerian economy.

4. Quoted companies should prioritize consistent and transparent dividend policies, as dividends serve as credible signals of firm performance and are highly valued by investors in Nigeria's capital market.
5. Firms and analysts should be cautious in relying solely on ROE as a measure of performance. Alternative value-based metrics such as Economic Value Added (EVA) or Cash Flow Return on Investment (CFROI) may offer better insights into shareholder value creation.
6. While maintaining adequate liquidity is essential, firms should avoid excessive idle cash. Strategic reinvestment of surplus liquidity into growth-generating activities may enhance investor confidence and long-term returns.
7. Large firms should streamline operations and reduce bureaucratic overhead to mitigate the negative impact of size on shareholder value. Corporate governance reforms and performance-based management structures may help improve efficiency.
8. Regulators and market educators should work to improve investor understanding of leverage and capital structure, especially in contexts where debt financing is underutilized or misunderstood.

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